

VIRTIGATION – Emerging viral diseases in tomatoes and cucurbits: Implementation of mitigation strategies for durable disease management

Deliverable 4.2

A report on the role of seed transmission on viral disease spread to Europe with implications on policies importing vegetable seeds

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D4.2 A report on the role of seed transmission on viral disease spread to Europe with implications on policies importing vegetable seeds

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

EFSA - European Food Safety Authority
EPPO – European Plant Protection Organization
PCR – Polymerase chain reaction
PRA – Pest risk assessment
QP - Quarantine Pest
RNQP - Regulated Non-Quarantine Pest
ToLCNDV – Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus
ToBRFV – Tomato brown rugose fruit virus
ToLCVD – Tomato leaf curl virus disease
TMV - Tobacco mosaic virus
ToMV - Tomato mosaic virus
ToMMV - Tomato mottle mosaic virus
UAS-B - University of Agricultural Sciences - Bengaluru

1 PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

In this task, we investigated the possibilities for the long-distance dispersal of viruses via seed. We focused our work on the two fast spreading viruses in Europe: the tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (ToLCNDV) and tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV). We investigated both 'seed-borne' and 'seed-transmitted' nature of both viruses. Seed-borne viruses can be present and detected on the seed but will not spread to new crop and thus they pose no threat to the new environment, while seed-transmitted viruses are present on seeds, can be detected and spread to the new environment and thus pose a threat to the new environment it was introduced into.

This document is prepared in two parts; ToLCNDV and ToBRFV separately because of the nature of the viruses being DNA and RNA viruses, respectively, which required different types of investigations. For ToLCNDV, we first investigated the seed-borne nature of the virus by detecting the virus by PCR in four major cucurbit vegetable crops of India such as bitter melon, bottle gourd, ridge gourd and pumpkin. We found that ToLCNDV was present in varying levels in seeds of different crops from 0% to 6.0% in bottle gourd and bitter melon, respectively (over 3500 PCR tests conducted). The virus was present in the embryo of only bitter melon, which raised the possibility of seed-transmitted nature of the virus. Thus, two further experiments were conducted: seed to seedling transmission and grow out tests. In seed to seedling transmission experiments, seeds of all four vegetables were grown in germination papers but found no transmission of the virus from seed to young seedlings by PCR tests. Similar results were obtained in grow out tests on plants grown for two months from infected seeds. Our results agreed with two independent studies from Spain, which also detected ToLCNDV in cucurbit seeds, but the virus was not transmitted to new plants. However, this contradicted some other studies from India, Taiwan and South Korea which have confirmed high levels of seed transmission of ToLCNDV (up to 70%). We therefore support EPPO's conclusion that seed-transmission of ToLCNDV is currently debatable and this is not universal and may be specific to some virus strains and the crop plants they infect. More work is therefore needed before drawing generalized conclusions, and further support EPPO's conclusions on retaining ToLCNDV as a risk for the EU based on its current impact.

We conducted similar experiments on ToBRFV and found that the virus was present on the coats of tomato seeds, embedded firmly between the seed trichomes (hair). The virus was detectable in seeds by ELISA, RT-PCR and microscopic observations. We then conducted extensive grow out tests and found that ToBRFV was seed-transmissible at very low levels of 0.025% (2 infected seedlings out of 8000). These results are similar to earlier studies that also showed low levels of seed to seedling transmission of 0.08%. The PRA concluded that the likelihood of an entry pathway of ToBRFV via tomato seeds was as high and our results support this conclusion. In this document, we have several further recommendations on seed sampling size, sampling rate, and diagnostic tests for minimizing the risk of moving ToBRFV within and into the EU.

2 A REPORT ON THE ROLE OF SEED TRANSMISSION ON VIRAL DISEASE SPREAD TO EUROPE WITH IMPLICATIONS ON POLICIES IMPORTING VEGETABLE SEEDS

Preface and definitions:

Based on seed infections, viruses can be classified into two types: “**Seed-borne viruses**” and “**seed-transmitted viruses**”. A seed-borne virus is defined as the ability of a virus to be carried through seeds, which does not necessarily lead to transmission to the next generation of plants but can be detectable by diagnostic tests. This is akin to seed contamination where the virus is carried passively on the seed but does not lead to infection of new plants grown from such seeds. These types of viruses are often docile with no real threat to the new environment they were introduced into. In contrast, a seed-transmitted virus is defined as the ability of a virus to be carried through seeds which can lead to transmission to the next generation of plants from which the virus can spread further to a new crop. These will pose a significant threat to the new environment as they can lead to infections. In both cases, however, the virus can be detectable using diagnostic methods. In this document, we investigated both types of seed infections for the two invading viruses: tomato leaf curl New Delhi Virus (ToLCNDV) and tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV), which are outlined below.

3 TOMATO LEAF CURL NEW DELHI VIRUS (BEGOMOVIRUS, GEMINIVIRIDAE)

About 48 species of begomoviruses (family Geminiviridae) are known to cause the tomato leaf curl virus disease (ToLCVD) worldwide. The ToLCNDV, first reported from India in 1995, is one of the major species causing ToLCVD (Padidam *et al.*, 1995). Since then, ToLCNDV has spread to many countries in Southeast Asia, the Middle East and more recently to Europe in 2014 (Chang *et al.*, 2010; Ito *et al.*, 2008; Zaidi *et al.*, 2017; Moriones *et al.*, 2017). In addition to tomatoes, ToLCNDV infects a wide range of host plants including beans, carrots, chilli pepper, cotton, cucurbits, okra, potatoes, soybean and tobacco (Moriones *et al.*, 2017). The ToLCNDV currently distributed in the Mediterranean region specifically infects cucurbits causing outbreak of a severe cucurbit leaf curl disease in Europe (Fortes *et al.*, 2016; Moriones *et al.*, 2017). High genetic diversity in ToLCNDV is seen because of high rates of mutations and recombination between and within the species of begomoviruses, and this is considered the main reason for their ability to jump host from initially tomatoes to many other hosts recently. Infection of cucurbit in Europe is particularly interesting because ToLCNDV European strain mainly infects cucurbits, not tomatoes.

In addition, to expanding its host and geographical ranges, the ToLCNDV appears expanding its mode of spread too. The seed transmission of the ToLCNDV Indian strain was first discovered in chayote in India (Sangeetha *et al.*, 2018). The virus was detected using PCR in various parts of the fruit and seed, including pericarp, mesocarp, seed coat, endosperm, and embryo. Although plants grown from infected seeds were symptomless, the virus was detected in 25% of the plants, providing the first evidence of seed transmission. In contrast, Fortes *et al.* (2023) investigated the possible seed transmission of ToLCNDV ‘Spain’ strain from melon seeds as an alternative mechanism for long-distance virus spread. The virus was detected in floral parts and mature seeds of melon indicating the virus was seed-borne. Treatment with a chemical disinfectant significantly reduced the detectable virus associated with melon seeds, suggesting ToLCNDV was probably an external contamination of

the seed coat. ToLCNDV was also detectable at low levels when seed cotyledons and embryo were analyzed by quantitative PCR amplification, suggesting the potential for viral contamination or infection of the internal portions of seed. However, grow-out studies conducted with melon progeny plants germinated from seeds collected from ToLCNDV-infected plants did not support the transmission of virus from seeds to offspring. Other studies examining the seed infection of ToLCNDV are summarized in the below table.

Table 1. Studies documenting the seed transmission of ToLCNDV.

Host species	Type and % infection*	Country	Reference
Chayote (<i>Sechium edule</i>)	Seed-borne - 100% Seed-transmitted – 25%	India	Sangeetha et al. (2018)
Zucchini squash (<i>Cucurbita pepo</i>)	Seed-borne - 100% Seed-transmitted – 61.3%	South Korea	Kil et al. (2020)
Bitter gourd (<i>Momordica charantia</i>)	Seed-borne - 76% Seed-transmitted – 5%	India	Gomathi Devi et al. (2023)
Cucumber (<i>Cucumis sativus</i>)	Seed-borne - 79% Pollen-transmitted – 70%	Taiwan	Chang et al. (2023)
Melon (<i>Cucumis melo</i>)	Seed-borne - Yes Seed-transmitted - 0%	Spain	Fortes et al. (2023)
Cucurbits (<i>Citrullus lanatus</i> , <i>Cucumis melo</i> , <i>Cucurbita moschata</i> , <i>Cucurbita pepo</i> and <i>Cucumis sativus</i>)	Seed-borne - 100% Seed-transmitted – 0%	Spain	Saez et al. (2023)

*Pollen-transmitted was concluded as seed-transmissible.

3.1 Data derived from the Virtigation project

Task 4.2: Determine the role and importance of seed transmission in long-distance dissemination of viruses

3.1.1 Study material:

This study was conducted on five popular cucurbit vegetables of India: bitter gourd, ridge gourd, pumpkin, bottle gourd and cucumber. Fruits were collected from naturally virus-infected plants in farmers' fields in the state of Karnataka, India in the 2022-2023 season. The plants were confirmed to be infected with ToLCNDV in the lab by PCR at the University of Agricultural Sciences-Bengaluru (UAS-B). Seeds were extracted from fruits, air dried and used in three independent experiments for virus testing, germination experiments and grow-out tests (see below).

3.1.2 PCR testing of seeds for ToLCNDV:

Both the external (seed coat) and internal infection (pericarp, embryo) of seeds by ToLCNDV was tested by PCR. For determining the external seed-borne nature of the virus, total DNA was extracted by vigorously shaking the seeds in the cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) buffer (Lodhi *et al.*,

1994) and the extracts were used in PCR using ToLCNDV-specific primers. Two hundred seeds were tested for each plant species except for cucumber for which no seeds were available in the infected plants. So, a total of 800 seeds were tested for the external infection of seeds by ToLCNDV and found that the bitter gourd had the highest rate of infection at 6% while no infection was found for bottle gourd (Table 2).

For testing the internal infections of ToLCNDV, the seed coat, endosperm and embryo were individually tested for the presence of the virus from the same 200 seeds from all four plant species, making it a total of 2400 PCR tests. The infection levels were highest for bitter gourd (3.1%) and nil for bottle gourd (0.0%) (Table 2). Infection of embryo (2.5%) was seen only in bitter gourd but not in others. The overall infection levels are much lower in our experiments compared to previous studies (Table 1).

Table 2: Testing the seed borne nature of ToLCNDV in different vegetables in Virtigation

Crops	No. of seeds tested	External seed infection rate	Internal seed infection rate
Bitter gourd	<i>Momordica charantia</i>	6.0%	3.1%
Ridge gourd	<i>Luffa acutangula</i>	5.0%	2.0%
Pumpkin	<i>Cucurbita pepo</i>	3.0%	1.1%
Bottle gourd	<i>Lagenaria siceraria</i>	0.0%	0.0%

To investigate the seed-transmitted nature of ToLCNDV, we carried out two separate experiments: seedling germination and grow-out tests.

3.1.3 Seedling germination test:

Fifty seeds each of bitter gourd, ridge gourd, pumpkin and bottle gourd were sown in germination papers (total 200 seeds) and the 10-15 days old seedlings were tested for ToLCNDV by PCR. Virus was not detected in any of the seedlings.

3.1.4 Grow-out tests:

Another set of 50 seeds each from bitter gourd, ridge gourd, pumpkin and bottle gourd were sown in insect proof cages in the glasshouse at UAS-B and the rate of ToLCNDV transmission was recorded at 30 and 60 days after sowing. None of the nearly 200 plants grown showed any disease symptoms during their growth cycle and they were also PCR negative for ToLCNDV at both time points.

These results are contrasting to previous studies which showed between 5 and 61.3% seed-transmission of ToLCNDV to new crops (Table 1). Together, these results indicate the dynamic nature of seed transmission by ToLCNDV and it appears that this is plant and virus strain specific. For example, if an aggressive form of ToLCNDV is infecting a very susceptible plant, and if that plant can produce seeds despite virus infection, it may be possible for seed transmission to occur (see Sandra and Mandal, 2024). The previous cases of ToLCNDV seed-transmission were shown in India, Taiwan and South Korea, however, our results are in agreement with two independent studies from Spain (Table 1), which showed that ToLCNDV can be seed-borne but not seed-transmissible.

3.1.5 Pest Risk Analyses of ToLCNDV, EPPO 2020, and recommendations:

The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) on Plant Health (2020) classifies the seed transmissibility of begomoviruses as uncertain and debated, which is an accurate summary of the current evidence for ToLCNDV and until more concrete evidence can be obtained, conclusions can only be drawn for a particular strain of the virus and variety specific, and not generalised. However, the virus is regulated under Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/2072. The main pathway of entry identified is planting of susceptible hosts, even if entry could also occur via commodities carrying viruliferous *B. tabaci* and possibly by seeds.

The main uncertainties associated with the pest categorisation of ToLCNDV are the distribution and prevalence of the virus in the EU, the magnitude of the virus impact particularly on hosts different from Cucurbitaceae, and seed transmission. ToLCNDV meets all the criteria evaluated by EFSA to qualify as potential Union Quarantine Pest (QP); conversely, ToLCNDV does not meet the criterion of being widespread in the EU to qualify as a Regulated Non-Quarantine Pest (RNQP). Should new data show that ToLCNDV is widespread in the EU, the possibility would exist for non-EU isolates to qualify as QP, while ToLCNDV EU isolates (ToLCNDV-ES) could qualify as RNQP.

In a country-specific analyses, EPPO concludes that the most likely introduction route of ToLCNDV into Poland, for example, is through import of infected material. Systematic controls to detect the presence of virus (or infection symptoms) can reduce probability of introduction and spread. The protection against viruses is based on systematic monitoring of imported plant material. Infected plants and vectors need to be removed and destroyed. It will ensure adequate protection against virus development in PRA area. Cultivations of host plants need to be systematically monitored in case of pathogen occurrence in Poland. The European Food Safety Authority considers ToLCNDV and its vector *Bemisia tabaci* as a risk to Europe and it should remain characterised as a risk. No outright seed testing for ToLCNDV is recommended as of now although we should be vigilant on the source of seed production including if the seed is produced in an area endemic to ToLCNDV and the seed comes from germplasm/ varieties susceptible to the virus.

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4 TOMATO BROWN RUGOSE FRUIT VIRUS (TOBAMOVIRUS)

The tobamovirus tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV), first reported in 2016 (Salem et al., 2016) infects tomato plants harboring the *Tm-2²* resistance allele (Luria et al., 2017), which conferred resistance against other tomato infecting tobamoviruses: tobacco mosaic virus (TMV), tomato mosaic virus (ToMV) and tomato mottle mosaic virus (ToMMV) (Lanfermeijer et al., 2003; Lanfermeijer et al., 2004; Nagai et al., 2019; Tetey et al., 2023). Similar to other tobamoviruses ToBRFV is a seed-borne mechanically transmitted virus (Broadbent, 1965) that contaminates the tomato seeds confined to the seed coat and the covering hair-like trichomes as observed by immunofluorescence (Klap et al., 2020a) and other serological assays (Salem et al., 2022; Matsushita et al., 2024) or RT-qPCR of isolated seed coats (Davino et al., 2020).

Although ToBRFV was not found in the embryo of developed seeds, contaminated seeds could initiate infection presumably by mechanical transmission through cuts occurring during germination (Dombrovsky & Smith, 2017). Studies of ToBRFV grow out experiments reported a wide range of seed to seedlings transmission ratios. Transmission ratios of 2.8% and 1.8% were reported by testing cotyledons (500) and third true leaves (500), respectively using RT-qPCR (Davino et al., 2020). Using ELISA test of 1187 seedlings a transmission ratio of 0.08% was reported (Salem et al., 2022). Using 192 seeds, 9 plants (4.7%) were positive as tested by RT-PCR however, the seeds were not thoroughly washed before sowing (Matsushita et al., 2024).

4.1 Data derived from Virtigation project

Task 4.2: Determine the role and importance of seed transmission in long-distance dissemination of viruses

4.1.1 Calculations of seed to seedling transmission ratios (Dombrovsky and Lapidot Labs).

4.1.1.1 Seed source used for grow out experiments:

Tomato seedlings were sap mechanically inoculated with ToBRFV 14 days post planting. The ToBRFV-infected plants were propagated, showing symptoms characteristic of ToBRFV disease. Insect pollinator were not employed. Fruits were harvested from clusters 3-4 and following squeezing the fruits the pulp was fermented for 16h followed by extensive washes with water only. Seeds were collected, dried and served for sowing for the grow out experiments.

Twenty independent grow out experiments were conducted with 200-500 seeds in each replica. The experiments were performed in two separate lab infrastructures in a restricted compound under hygienic conditions. At 40-50 days post germination leaf samples were collected for ELISA or RT-PCR assays. The calculated seed to seedling transmission ratio was 0.025% (2 infected seedlings out of 8000).

Our results resemble the above presented reported seed to seedling ratio of 0.08% (Salem et al., 2022). **Importantly**, even a low percentage of contaminated seeds can cause a multitude of infection foci (Maule & Wang, 1996) that spread rapidly by mechanical contact and adherence to surfaces (Broadbent & Fletcher, 1963; Klap et al., 2020b; Panno et al., 2020; Ehlers et al., 2023; Skelton et al., 2023).

4.1.1.2 In the Pest Risk Analysis for ToBRFV (PRA) 2020

Likelihood of an entry pathway of ToBRFV *via* tomato seeds was determined as high. Likelihood of entry should be kept high due to the mechanical spread from a small number of infectious foci described above. Moderate uncertainty should be changed to low uncertainty due to the wide range of transmission rate in grow out experiments.

4.1.1.3 In ISHI-Veg ISF 2019

RT-qPCR is recommended as the method to test seeds and the positive results are confirmed by a local lesion assay (a biological assay). The minimum recommended sample size is 3000 seeds and a maximum sub-sample size of 250. These recommendations should be kept.

4.1.1.4 In the COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING REGULATION (EU) 2023/1032 of 25 May 2023

A differential sampling testing rate is required depending on the seed source country. For example, 50% of the consignment of seeds coming from highly infected regions is required to be tested. Sampling size rate needs to be kept high.

Articles 8 and 10 regarding movement of specified seeds within the European Union or into the Union should be kept. Seed sampling will be conducted by applying a hypergeometric sampling scheme (sampling without replacements).

4.1.1.5 Future prospect:

- New alternative methodology based on a large segment (LS-PCR) amplification followed by an additional small fragment amplification could replace the classical local lesion biological assay and needs to be developed and validated.
- Seed disinfection protocol needs to be developed and validated and could be used by all seed companies.
- The new developed technology (LS-PCR) could allow prediction of infectivity potential of the amplified viral genome extracted from the tested seed samples. This methodology may be useful for testing disinfected seed lots that were detected positive by the regular SE-PCR and the viral genome is fragmented with no infectivity potential.

4.1.1.6 Seeds of resistant and tolerant varieties

Recent studies reported on ToBRFV natural mutants overcoming the newly developed resistant varieties (Jewehan et al., 2022; Kubota et al., 2024; Zisi et al., 2024).

Now, on May 2024, it is too early to foresee the potential interactions between the new varieties derived from different breeding programs and seed companies, harbouring a range of tolerant and resistant genes, and the ToBRFV genome plasticity.

Therefore, we suggest continuing with the regular seed testing for seeds of the newly developed tomato varieties until more data will be gathered to re-assess the potential risks.

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ANNEX 1: Some data and figures from seed transmission experiments.

Figure 1. The proportion of internally seed-borne nature of ToLCNDV in different Indian cucurbit vegetables in farmer's fields.

Figure 2. Presence of ToBRFV particles in seed trichomes in healthy and infected seeds.

Figure 3. A diagrammatic presentation of extraction of seeds from tomatoes for investigating ToBRFV seed transmission experiments